

Awareness and Acceptance of the Philosophy, Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives of the School of Education: Stakeholders' Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

The Philosophy, Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO) of the School of Education at San Isidro College served as the main highlights of this study, with the rallying points on the evaluation of the objectives and the assessment of the awareness and acceptance of the VMGO by the stakeholders, which include the faculty, students, and alumni. One hundred forty-nine respondents served as the online participants of the study. Their role is to evaluate the statements in the objectives as to their agreement on what is stated and to assess their agreement on their awareness and acceptance of the VMGO of the School of Education. Findings revealed that the stakeholders *strongly agreed* to the objectives as stated indicative of their clarity and relevance. Majority of the respondents also *affirmed* their awareness of the School of Education's VMGO as well as their acceptance of these as the essential *raison d'être* of San Isidro College's existence.

Subject Area

VGMO Evaluation

Keywords: *Awareness, Acceptance, VGMO, Stakeholders*

INTRODUCTION

Even in the incunabula of the school's existence the development of a school's mission statement represents the school's readiness and willingness to take charge of its own affairs and to manage change positively in the light of its vision. The school's philosophy, mission and vision statements are the bases of a school's policies and practices. There is no doubt that the values and beliefs that guide the life of the school have important bearing of its vision, mission, goals and objectives (VMGO).

The mission and vision of a school must be developed and clarified through a process of shared reflection on the values, beliefs and aspirations of the school community. They will reflect the school's efforts to reconcile conflicting values within the school community (Vanderelst, 2017). The awareness and acceptance of the vision and mission of the school is important. A school can accommodate a range of objectives provided there is a range of core values. The time spent in exploring the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the school is time well spent and will affect everything else done in the school.

Why is it important that the stakeholders are aware and have accepted the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the school? Most often people look into the “what” of something, instead of the “why” of that thing. If people never get at the why, all the activities, plans, projects become dull things to check off the to-do list in order to survive the day. Yet, all these should be geared toward helping students learn, grow, and become the best versions of themselves. There should be a common vernacular, that is, values that the community agrees as important — a why that compels students, educators, and parents to pull in the same direction allowing the school to become mission-driven (Woytek, 2018). It is the “why” that keeps the school going. “Why” for instance is San Isidro College still in existence for the past 70 years? This “Why” is the vision and mission of San Isidro College. Why do teachers persist to continue to teach at San Isidro College when they could very well transfer to a state school or public school and enjoy the tenure and retirement benefits? Very likely, teachers persist because of those lightbulb moments that their students have or maybe on their lightbulb moments to reflect on the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the school.

It would seem that people take the vision and mission of a school for granted and relatively unimportant. Yet, developing the school's vision and mission are two of the most important steps toward creating a successful program. Done well, they give clarity and direction for a school. A muddy vision or mission can help lead to continuing conflicts, and a school that has difficulty in identifying priorities. One proverb states “*Without a vision, the people perish*” (centerforschool, n.d.). The stakeholders especially the faculty, students, alumni and the community need to be aware and to understand the vision and mission of the school.

San Isidro College has its vision, mission, goals and objectives (VMGO). It also has its core values and graduate attributes that an Isidran graduate should possess. Every unit/school in the College also has its own VMGO that are patterned and framed from the home-based VGMO.

In preparation for the PAASCU accreditation, the School of Education (SED) revisited its VMGO and realized that the objectives of the SED are not articulated clearly. The graduate attributes served to mirror its objectives as these gave the focal outcomes of what will become of a SED graduate. Because of the seemingly unwritten objectives, the dean had a meeting with the faculty to craft the objectives which have to be presented for consultation to the stakeholders. Awareness and acceptance of the VMGO is one concern of the PAASCU accreditation, hence after the meeting and consultation with the faculty, the objectives were floated online via Google Meet. Virtual consultation with the faculty, students, and alumni was through a questionnaire via the Google Meet.

This study would therefore examine the evaluation of the stakeholders on their awareness and acceptance of the VMGO, and the evaluation as to the agreement of the stakeholders on the objectives of the SED as stated based from the graduate attributes of the College.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Mission and vision both relate to an organization's purpose and aspirations, and are typically communicated in some form of brief written statements. A mission statement communicates the organization's reason for being and how it aspires to serve its key stakeholders. The anchorage of formulating the vision and mission of an institution comes from the *Theory of Change*, which can be traced to Peter Drucker's articulation of *Management by Objectives*, popularized in his 1954 book "*The Practice of Management*". Theory of Change emerged from the field of program theory and program evaluation in the mid-1990s as a new way of analyzing the theories motivating programs and initiatives working for social and political change (Weiss, 1995). The theory requires identifying higher-order Goals, and lower-order Objectives which, if achieved, are expected to result in the Goals being achieved. Theory of Change extends beyond Goals (commonly named *Outcomes* in Theory of Change terminology) and Objectives to include Impact – the anticipated result of achieving stated goals (Wikipedia, n.d.)

Theory of Change is focused not just on generating knowledge about whether a program is effective, but also on explaining what methods it uses to be effective (Chris, et al., 2011). Theory of Change has strong roots in a number of disciplines, including environmental and organizational psychology, but has also increasingly been connected to sociology and political science (Stachowiak, 2010). This also goes true in the field of education, where institutions post their vision and mission for the stakeholders and the general public to see and read.

Vision and Mission of SED

The School of Education has for its vision:

“As a vibrant community of learners, the School of Education envisions to form professionals imbued with the high standards of excellence in education.”

The SED has for its mission:

“To produce dedicated and competent professional teachers for the Basic Education schools and who are sincere witnesses to the Gospel values.”

The Philosophy of the School of Education

As a *Filipino, Catholic, and Integral* Institution of Higher Learning, the School of Education at San Isidro College epitomizes the virtues of San Isidro Labrador and upholds the motto *Ora et Labora* which values prayer and work. Its philosophy embraces the following:

1. Education as centered in the Catholic faith where Jesus Christ is the model of total obedience to God the Father

The School of Education strives to make each learner realize his/her origin from God, and that through His Son Jesus Christ, the learners could emulate Him as the model for total obedience and surrender to the Will of the Father.

2. *Education as an integral and life-long process exemplifying the attributes of being God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service-oriented*

The School of Education instills in the learners that learning is an essential lifelong process guided by the graduate attributes on fear of the Lord, competence, disciplined, and as men and women for others. The ultimate goal is to achieve the harmonious development of knowledge, skills, experience, attitudes, values and virtues that will prepare them for life's challenges as they find their niches in the world.

3. *Education as a collaborative partnership between the school and the home in the Filipino community*

The School of Education believes that the collaborative endeavor of the home, school and the community would contribute to the wholistic development of the learners and will prepare them for life even after their formal schooling.

The SIC Graduate Attributes:

The SIC graduate attributes are the basis for the crafting of the SED's objectives. These graduate attributes include 4 characteristics.

First, is **God-Fearing** (*Faith in God*). The graduate must be professional and ethical teacher of Basic Education; God-fearing, competent, service-oriented and disciplined.

Second, is **Competent** (*Competence*). The graduate must be communicatively competent in spoken and written English and Filipino; Proficient in numeracy and problem solving; Competent and conversant with theories, concepts and principles of learning and their application; Adept at recognizing and using Basic Education students' physical, social, mental, emotional characteristics and needs in the educational process; Skilled in socio-civic, historical, and philosophical concepts and principles as applied in the teaching-learning tasks; Competent in choosing and utilizing tasks and activities from a repertoire of outcome-based teaching strategies; Competent in curriculum choice and preparation of materials for selected target learners; Versatile in planning and carrying out specific learning tasks with appropriate assessment; Proficient in critical decision-making processes to generate creative and innovative problem solutions and alternatives; Well-versed in national/international issues/concerns/advocacies and espouses those relevant to the profession.

Third, is **Disciplined** (*Self-Disciplined*). The graduate must be adept at recognizing and using Basic Education students' physical, social, mental, emotional characteristics and needs in the educational process; and is capable as a leader and model community member.

The fourth, is **Service-Oriented** (*Service Orientation*). The graduate must be capable as a leader and model community member; Professional ethical teacher of Basic Education.

The conceptual framework in this study as shown in Figure 1 illustrates the IPO model of input-process-output. The *Input variables* are the VMGO of San Isidro College. The Objectives are crafted in the *Process Variable*. Then there is consultation from the stakeholders as to their agreement of the objectives and as to whether they are aware and have accepted the VMGO of the School of Education. The *Output variables* show the results of the evaluation of the stakeholders on the objectives of SED and their assessment as to whether they are aware and have accepted the VGMO of the SED.

Figure 1. Teaching and Learning Engagements observed during the online class observations

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study evaluated the responses of the stakeholders when they were consulted online as to their agreement on the stated objectives of the School of Education and as to whether they are aware and have accepted the VMGO of the SED.

Specifically, it answered the following:

1. What is the percentage of agreement of the stakeholders on the San Isidro College School of Education’s Objectives?
2. What is the percentage of awareness and acceptance on the VGMO of the stakeholders of School of Education?

METHODOLOGY

San Isidro College, the only Catholic higher education institution in Malaybalay is the locale of this study. The College has been in existence for more than seven decades and as such it has already established its vision, mission, goals and objectives since its start of operation. The School of Education as one of its units has created in 1969 its course in secondary education and in 1995 for the elementary education to serve as its laboratory schools for the course offering in education.

The School of Education’s VMGO has for its springboard the VMGO of the College whose Philosophy centers on its being *Filipino, Catholic, and Integral Institution* of Higher Learning epitomizing the virtues of San Isidro Labrador and upholds the motto *Ora et Labora* that values prayer and work. The crafting of the VMGO of SED was done collectively by the administration, faculty, staff, students, alumni and other stakeholders and approved by the BUACs Board.

The PAASCU self-survey instrument is the basis where the instrument of the study was crafted. Since the SED has not clearly put into writing its objectives, this has to be well articulated this time when the school will be subjecting itself for the accreditation. Therefore, from the graduate attributes expected to be demonstrated by the SED graduates the objectives of the college was constructed.

After the construction of the objectives, these were presented to the faculty during the meeting for them to improve and make comments and suggestions. The plan was to have this open for consultation online to stakeholders like the faculty, students, alumni, and parents, considering that it is covid time and no group meetings are allowed.

The questionnaire simply asked the respondents to evaluate whether they agree on the objectives of the SED. Each objective is presented and the respondents would merely choose their responses from *strongly agree*, *agree*, *undecided*, *disagree*, and *strongly disagree*. These were floated via the Google Form. Another set of questionnaires asked them on their awareness and acceptance of the SED's VMGO. The questions were merely answerable by *Yes*, *Uncertain* or *No*. Again, this was floated via Google Form to the SED faculty, students, alumni, and parents. However, only the faculty, students and alumni responded and this is very understandable considering that these are the respondents who have access to the technology and to San Isidro College online platform.

A total of 149 participants were recorded among the respondents of the questionnaire. The respondents included 9 faculty members, 108 students, and 32 alumni. The whole month of July was the timeframe for gathering the responses.

Since the questionnaire is more of a survey, the results were simply treated using the frequency count and percentages. Each objective was taken singly, counting the frequency for those who *strongly agree*, *agree*, *uncertain*, *disagree* and *strongly disagree* with the statement. Then, their percentages were also computed. This procedure is to ascertain that each objective is taken distinctly as to how many evaluated this considering the extent of agreement of the stakeholders. Similarly, for the questionnaire on awareness and acceptance of the VMGO, the frequency and percentages were taken. More or less, the SED will be able to see that the objectives are clear and relevant if the percentage of agreement of a good number of respondents reaches at least 75%. The same percentage is applied to the result on the awareness and acceptance of the stakeholders of the SED's VGMO.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of the SED Objectives

Table 1 shows the result of the evaluation of the SED stakeholders on the crafted objectives of the school. The result of the survey shows the frequency and percentage of the stakeholders on their agreement to the SED Objectives.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage of stakeholders who agree/disagree on the objectives of the School of Education

Objectives of the School of Education	Strongly Agree		Agree		Uncertain		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
1. To instill in the students the Isidran attributes of being God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service oriented.	115	77	34	23	-	0	-	0	-	0
2. To become a professional and ethical teacher of Basic Education who is God-fearing and has faith in God.	116	78	31	21	2	1	-	0	-	0
3. To exhibit competence in written and spoken communication, proficient in mathematical skills, and conversant in theories and principles of teaching and learning.	99	66	49	32.5	1	0.5	-	0	-	0
4. To show versatility in planning and carrying out specific learning tasks with appropriate assessments	99	66	49	32.5	1	0.5	-	0	-	0
5. To develop competence in choosing and utilizing tasks and activities from a repertoire of outcome-based teaching strategies and in curriculum choice and preparation of materials for the learners	109	73	38	26	2	1	-	0	-	0
6. To demonstrate proficiency in critical decision making processes generating creative and innovative problem solutions and alternatives	100	67.5	46	31	2	1	1	0.5	-	0
7. To be adept at recognizing and using Basic Education student's physical, social, mental, emotional characteristics and needs in the educational process	105	70.5	41	28	2	1	1	0.5	-	0
8. To be skilled in socio-civic, historical, philosophical concepts and principles as applied in the teaching-learning tasks	103	69.5	43	29	2	1	1	0.5	-	0
9. To be well-versed in national and international issues/concerns/advocacies and espouses those relevant to the profession	97	65	49	33	3	2	-	0	-	0
10. To demonstrate capability as a leader and model community member contributing to the upliftment of life especially for the marginalized group through moral and legal means	107	71.5	40	26.5	2	1	-	0	-	0

As shown in Table 1, all the objectives have an *outstanding* percentage of agreement from the stakeholders. The number of respondents that agree to the objectives ranged from 146 to 149 indicating percentages from 98 to 100%. With this percentage of agreement, it is deduced that

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these objectives are clearly stated and are relevant, since these exceeds the 75% level set in this study.

The first objective “To instill in the students the Isidran attributes of being God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service oriented” got a 100% agreement from the stakeholders with 77% *strongly agreeing* and 23% *agreeing*. The four attributes of an Isidran graduate are stipulated in this objective that is God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service oriented. This objective really encompasses everything that is expected from an Isidran graduate.

Table 1.1. Assessment of Objective Number 1

SED Objectives	Respondents	5 (SA)		4 (A)		3 (U)	2 (D)	1 (SD)
		f	%	f	%			
Objective 1. <i>To instill in the students the Isidran attributes of being God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service oriented</i>	Alumni	29	19.46	3	2.01	-	-	-
	Faculty	7	4.69	2	1.34	-	-	-
	Student	79	53.02	29	19.46	-	-	-
	Total	155	77.18	34	22.82	-	-	-

The combined percentage of *strongly agree* and *agree* is 100% which indicates that the objective is *most acceptable*. In fact, this is the objective where all the respondents agree, either *strongly agree* or simply *agree*.

The third and fourth objectives “To exhibit competence in written and spoken communication, proficient in mathematical skills, and conversant in theories and principles of teaching and learning” and “To show versatility in planning and carrying out specific learning tasks with appropriate assessments” got a 99% of agreement from the stakeholders with 99 responding to *strongly agree* and 49 responding to *agree*. In these objectives, it is clear that the graduates are expected to be proficient in communication, mathematics and in teaching. They should know their work as a teacher, basically in teaching as well as in preparing assessment tools. As observed from the responses, there is one student respondent who answered *uncertain*. Very likely this student felt that he/she has not fully developed his/her competence in written and oral communication, mathematics, and in the theories and principles in teaching. There was no negative response. The combined percentage for *strongly agree* and *agree* is 99% which exceeds the set 75% for considering it acceptable, hence these objectives are accepted.

Table 1.2. Assessment of Objectives 3 and 4

SED Objectives	Respondents	5 (SA)		4 (A)		3 (U)		2 (D)	1 (SD)
		f	%	f	%	f	%		
Objective 3. <i>To exhibit competence in written and spoken communication, proficient in mathematical skills, and conversant in theories and principles of teaching and learning</i>	Alumni	23	15.44	9	6.04	-	-	-	-
	Faculty	5	4.02	4	2.68	-	-	-	-
	Student	71	47.68	36	24.16	1	0.67	-	-
	Total	99	66.44	49	32.89	1	0.67	-	-
Objective 4. <i>To show versatility in planning and carrying out specific learning tasks with appropriate assessments</i>	Alumni	24	16.11	8	5.36	-	-	-	-
	Faculty	5	3.35	4	2.68	-	-	-	-
	Student	70	46.98	37	24.83	1	0.67	-	-
	Total	99	66.44	49	32.89	1	0.67	-	-

The second, fifth and tenth objectives “To become a professional and ethical teacher of Basic Education who is God-fearing and has faith in God”, “To develop competence in choosing and utilizing tasks and activities from a repertoire of outcome-based teaching strategies and in curriculum choice and preparation of materials for the learners”, and “To demonstrate capability as a leader and model community member contributing to the upliftment of life especially for the marginalized group through moral and legal means”, got a 98.66% number of respondents who *agree*, indicating that these objectives are clear and relevant. For the 2nd objective 78% *strongly agree*, 21% *agree*, although 1% among the student was *uncertain*. The fifth objective shows that 73% *strongly agree*, 26% *agree* and 1% of the student was *uncertain*. The tenth objective shows that 71.5% *strongly agree*, 26.5% *agree*, and 1% of the students were *uncertain*. Again, it is evident that generally the stakeholders find these objectives clear and relevant, hence these objectives are accepted.

As observed from the results there were two out of the 108 students who responded that they were *uncertain*. It is also observed that although the faculty generally agrees to these objectives, some did not indicate strong agreement. For instance, in Objective 2, out of the nine faculty, six *strongly agreed* but the three merely agree. In Objective 5, out of the nine faculty, four *strongly agreed* while five just *agree*. Similarly, in Objective 10, out of the nine faculty, four *strongly agree* while five simply *agree*. What could be the implication to these? Could it be that the teachers agree that the graduates ought to develop these outcomes but still they doubt if they really can? Could it be that even if these objectives are essential for the graduate there is still a long way to be able to truly achieve these? Could it imply that even the teachers are doubtful if they could successfully deliver these objectives? Could it be that the teachers find the students less capable and therefore would not fully accomplish these objectives? These are some questions that need some reflections on the part of the faculty and of the students.

Table 1.3. Assessment of Objectives 2, 5, and 10.

SED Objectives	Respondents	5 (SA)		4 (A)		3 (U)		2 (D)	1 (SD)
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%		
Objective 2. <i>To become a professional and ethical teacher of Basic Education who is God-fearing and has faith in God</i>	Alumni	28	18.79	4	2.68	-	-	-	-
	Faculty	6	4.02	3	2.01	-	-	-	-
	Student	82	55.03	24	16.11	2	1.34	-	-
	Total	116	77.85	31	20.80	2	1.34	-	-
Objective 5. <i>To develop competence in choosing and utilizing tasks and activities from a repertoire of outcome-based teaching strategies and in curriculum choice and preparation of materials for the learners</i>	Alumni	26	14.45	6	4.02	-	-	-	-
	Faculty	4	2.68	5	3.35	-	-	-	-
	Student	79	53.02	27	18.12	2	1.34	-	-
	Total	109	73.15	38	25.50	2	1.34	-	-
Objective 10. <i>To demonstrate capability as a leader and model community member contributing to the upliftment of life especially for the marginalized group through moral and legal means</i>	Alumni	28	18.79	4	2.68	-	-	-	-
	Faculty	4	2.68	5	3.35	-	-	-	-
	Student	75	50.33	31	20.81	2	1.34	-	-
	Total	107	71.81	40	26.85	2	1.34	-	-

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Table 1.4 shows the rest of the objectives, i.e., 6, 7,8, and 9 reflects a 98% of agreement from the stakeholder, indicative of their being clearly stated and have relevance to the Isidran graduate.

Table 1.4. Assessment of Objectives 6, 7, 8, and 9.

SED Objectives	Respondents	5 (SA)		4 (A)		3 (U)		2 (D)		1 (SD)
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Objective 6. <i>To demonstrate proficiency in critical decision making processes generating creative and innovative problem solutions and alternatives</i>	Alumni	20	13.42	11	7.38	1	0.67	-	-	-
	Faculty	5	3.35	4	2.68	-	-	-	-	-
	Student	75	50.33	31	20.81	1	0.67	1	0.67	-
	Total	100	67.11	46	30.87	2	1.34	1	0.67	-
Objective 7. <i>To be adept at recognizing and using Basic Education student's physical, social, mental, emotional characteristics and needs in the educational process</i>	Alumni	24	11.16	8	5.37	-	-	-	-	-
	Faculty	5	3.35	4	2.68	-	-	-	-	-
	Student	76	51.01	29	19.46	2	1.34	1	0.67	-
	Total	105	70.47	41	27.52	2	1.34	1	0.67	-
Objective 8. <i>To be skilled in socio-civic, historical, philosophical concepts and principles as applied in the teaching-learning tasks</i>	Alumni	22	14.77	9	6.04	1	0.67	-	-	-
	Faculty	3	2.01	6	4.02	-	-	-	-	-
	Student	78	52.35	28	18.79	1	0.67	1	0.67	-
	Total	103	69.13	43	28.26	2	1.34	1	0.67	-
Objective 9. <i>To be well-versed in national and international issues/concerns/advocacies and espouses those relevant to the profession</i>	Alumni	18	12.08	13	8.72	1	0.67	-	-	-
	Faculty	5	3.35	4	2.68	-	-	-	-	-
	Student	74	49.66	32	21.48	2	1.34	-	-	-
	Total	97	65.11	49	32.89	3	2.01	-	-	-

In the overall picture, looking into the frequency and percentages of the respondents who strongly agreed to the stated objectives, it is observed that Objective 2 has the most number, followed by Objective 1, third is Objective 5, followed by Objective 10, 7, 8, 6, 3&4, and 9.

The number of participants who responded on *agreeing* to the objectives shows objectives 3,4 & 9 have the highest frequencies, followed by Objective 6, 8,7,10, 5, 1, and 2. There were one, two and three participants who were *uncertain*, with 2 participants in objectives 2, 4 to 8 and 10, while objectives 3 and 9 has one participant each who were *uncertain*.

One student participant who *disagreed* can be seen in Objectives 6, 7, and 8. These objectives include “To demonstrate proficiency in critical decision making processes generating creative and innovative problem solutions and alternatives”, “To be adept at recognizing and using Basic Education student’s physical, social, mental, emotional characteristics and needs in the educational process”, and “To be skilled in socio-civic, historical, philosophical concepts and principles as applied in the teaching-learning tasks”. While there was only one deviating opinion, it is still good to look into the content of these objectives and analyze how these could be improved.

In a nutshell, the online consultation with the stakeholders on the objectives of the School of Education showed that the combined percentages of those who *strongly agree* and those who simply agree exceeds the 75% level, hence all the objectives are accepted. The evaluation from the stakeholders is a good academic exercise that could help to strengthen the objectives of the SED. This exercise is a good vehicle to keep the stakeholders aware of the SED's VMGO and to realize that SIC recognizes the participation and involvement of the stakeholders in important decision making.

Awareness and Acceptance of the Stakeholders on the VMGO of the School of Education

The second problem in this study is to assess the awareness and acceptance of the VMGO by the stakeholders. The VMGO of SIC relate to its purpose and aspirations. The mission and vision statements communicate the SIC's reason for being and how it aspires to serve its stakeholders. It is therefore essential that these stakeholders should be aware and should accept the VMGO of the school.

The VMGO provide a vehicle for communicating an organization's purpose and values to all key stakeholders. Typically, these statements would be widely circulated and discussed often so that their meaning is widely understood, shared, and internalized. The better the stakeholders understand the VMGO, the better they will understand the school's programs, projects and activities. The better they will become aware and knowledgeable on the VMGO and they could accept these within their hearts.

Table 2 reflects the awareness and acceptance of the stakeholders on the VMGO of the SED. As shown in the result of the survey on the awareness and acceptance of the VMGO of the SED, majority of the participants responded affirmatively from 140 to 148 out of the 149 participants. The first 8 questions were related to awareness and acceptance of the VGMO. The *awareness* items were in 1, 3, 5, and 7 and the *acceptance* items were in 2,4,6, and 8. The highest item was on the "acceptance of the mission of SED" with 99.5% responding affirmatively and only 0.5% who were *uncertain*.

Generally, the participants gave a 95 to a 99.5% *Yes* rating on their awareness and acceptance of the VGMO. The implication to this result indicates that the stakeholders are aware of the VMGO of SED. They have knowledge and they are well-informed about the VMGO of SED. This could be because the VMGO are posted in every classroom of the school. These are also given during the orientation of the students. These are explained to them and they are told to put these in their minds and hearts because these are the expected things that they must do as an Isidran graduate.

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Table 2. Awareness and Acceptance of the Stakeholders on the VMGO of the School of Education.

Awareness and Acceptance of the VMGO of the SED	Yes		Uncertain		No	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
1. I am aware of the vision of the School of Education.	147	99	2	1	-	-
2. I accept the vision of the School of Education.	147	99	2	1	-	-
3. I am aware of the mission of the School of Education.	142	95	7	5	-	-
4. I accept the mission of the School of Education	148	99.5	1	0.5	-	-
5. I am aware of the goals of the School of Education.	142	95	7	5	-	-
6. I accept the goals of the School of Education	146	98	3	2	-	-
7. I am aware of the objectives of the School of Education.	142	95	7	5	-	-
8. I accept the objectives of the School of Education.	147	99	2	1	-	-
9. The vision-mission-goals –objectives of the School of Education are clearly stated	145	97	4	3	-	-
10. The vision-mission-goals are in harmony with national goals and desirable Filipino cultural values.	148	99.5	1	0.5	-	-
11. The vision-mission-goals of the institution are published in a catalogue or prospectus.	143	96	6	4	-	-
12. There is harmony between actual educational practices and activities and the stated vision, mission, goals and objectives.	140	94	9	6	-	-
13. The Mission, Vision, goals and objectives are adapted to the educational needs of the local, regional, and national community.	145	97	4	3	-	-
14. The institution includes among its goals the completion of an adequate program of general education by each of its students.	144	96.65	5	3.35	-	-

Specifically, Table 2.1 reflects the items that indicated the awareness of the stakeholders of the SED's VMGO. From the result of the survey, scrutinizing the awareness items for 1, 3, 5, and 7, generally the stakeholders were *very much aware* of the VMGO of SED. Their awareness ranged from 95.30% to 98.66%, indicating that they *strongly agree* that they are aware of the VMGO. There are a few who responded that they were *uncertain* as to whether they agree or not. However, these were minimal from 0.67% to 4.70%. In spite of the few who were *uncertain*, still, there is a need for SED to look into the VMGO and to enhance the awareness of these during the orientation period and during students' forum and convocations. It is understandable that they seem not to be aware of the objectives because these are presented as graduate attributes of the college. It is for this reason why the SED has really to state these objectives distinctly. As a whole the SED stakeholders generally affirmed their awareness on the VMGO. The non-awareness of the VMGO were from the students and the alumni, although in item 5 and 7 one faculty responded with an *uncertain* answer.

Table 2.1. Awareness and Acceptance of the Stakeholders on the VMGO of the School of Education.

Awareness of the VMGO	Respondents	YES		UNCERTAIN		NO
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	
1. I am aware of the vision of the School of Education	Alumni	31	20.81	1	0.67	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	107	71.81	1	0.67	-
	Total	147	98.66	2	1.34	-
3. I am aware of the mission of the School of Education	Alumni	30	20.13	2	1.34	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	103	69.13	5	3.36	-
	Total	142	95.30	7	4.70	-
5. I am aware of the goals of the School of Education	Alumni	30	20.13	2	1.34	-
	Faculty	8	5.37	1	0.67	-
	Student	104	69.80	4	2.68	-
	Total	142	95.30	7	4.70	-
7. I am aware of the objectives of the School of Education	Alumni	29	19.46	3	2.01	-
	Faculty	8	5.37	1	0.67	-
	Student	105	70.47	4	2.68	-
	Total	142	95.30	7	4.70	-

Table 2,2 shows the items on *acceptance*, found in numbers 2,4,6, and 8. The results of the survey generally show that the stakeholders *accepted* very well the VMGO of SED. The group showed a *very high* percentage of acceptances from 97.99% to 99.33%. This means that out of the 149 respondents, there were 146 to 148 who responded with a resounding yes. There was no negative response, which indicates that the stakeholders accepted the VMGO of the SED. However, there were sprinkles of *uncertainty* from the students' group. Out of the 108 students one to three of them were not sure to accept some of the items. Although there were three students and one alumna who responded with their uncertainty, the general picture indicates that the VMGO were clearly stated.

Table 2.2. Acceptance on the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the School of Education.

Awareness of the VMGO	Respondents	YES		UNCERTAIN		NO
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	
2. I accept the vision of the School of Education	Alumni	32	21.48	-	-	-
	Faculty	9	6.08	-	-	-
	Student	106	71.14	2	1.34	-
	Total	147	98.66	2	1.34	-
4. I accept the mission of the School of Education	Alumni	32	21.48	-	-	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	107	71.81	1	0.67	-
	Total	148	99.33	1	0.67	-
6. I accept the goals of the School of Education	Alumni	31	20.81	1	0.67	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	106	71.14	2	1.34	-
	Total	146	97.99	3	2.01	-
8. I accept the objectives of the School of Education	Alumni	32	21.48	-	-	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	106	71.14	2	1.34	-
	Total	147	98.66	2	1.34	-

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The acceptance on the mission of SED got a very high percentage turn-out from the respondents, since only one student from the total 149 respondents was uncertain of his/her response. The SED has for its mission: “*To produce dedicated and competent professional teachers for the Basic Education schools and who are sincere witnesses to the Gospel values.*”

Table 2.3 shows the acceptance and awareness of the stakeholders on the characteristic features of the SED’s VMGO. These are on items 9 to 14. As shown in the Table, majority of the stakeholders indicated awareness and acceptance on the characteristic features of the SED’s VMGO. There were no negative responses. Item no. 9 shows that 97.32% agreed to this with an affirmative response. Item no. 10 “The vision-mission-goals are in harmony with national goals and desirable Filipino cultural values” shows that 99.5% of the respondents answered this affirmatively. This implies that the stakeholders agree that the VMGO of the SED are in sync with the national goals and the Filipino cultural values.

Table 2.3. Awareness and acceptance on the characteristic of the SED’s VMGO.

Awareness of the VMGO	Respondents	YES		UNCERTAIN		NO
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	
9. The vision-mission-goals – objectives of the School of Education are clearly stated	Alumni	31	29.81	1	0.67	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	105	70.47	3	2.01	-
	Total	145	97.32	4	2.68	-
10. The vision-mission-goals are in harmony with national goals and desirable Filipino cultural values.	Alumni	32	21.48	-	-	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	107	71.81	1	0.67	-
	Total	148	99.33	1	0.67	-
11. The vision-mission-goals of the institution are published in a catalogue or prospectus.	Alumni	30	20.13	2	1.34	-
	Faculty	8	5.37	1	0.67	-
	Student	105	70.47	3	2.01	-
	Total	143	95.97	6	4.02	-
12. There is harmony between actual educational practices and activities and the stated vision, mission, goals and objectives	Alumni	29	19.46	3	2.01	-
	Faculty	9	6.04	-	-	-
	Student	102	68.46	6	4.02	-
	Total	140	93.96	9	6.04	-
13. The Mission, Vision, goals and objectives are adapted to the educational needs of the local, regional, and national community.	Alumni	32	21.48	-	-	-
	Faculty	8	5.37	1	0.67	-
	Student	105	70.47	3	2.01	-
	Total	145	97.32	4	2.68	-
14. The institution includes among its goals the completion of an adequate program of general education by each of its students	Alumni	32	21.48	-	-	-
	Faculty	8	5.37	1	0.67	-
	Student	104	69.80	4	2.68	-
	Total	144	96.64	5	3.36	-

Item No. 11 “The vision-mission-goals of the institution are published in a catalogue or prospectus” indicated 95.87% respondents who answered yes. There are however six respondents from the alumni, faculty and students who answered *uncertain*. Most likely, they have seen the prospectus with the VMGO but they have not seen the catalogue. Item No. 12 “There is harmony between actual educational practices and activities and the stated vision, mission, goals and objectives” shows that 94% of the respondents rated this as yes. So far, all the items got a 94 to

99.5% “yes”, indicating that they faculty, students and alumni are aware of the VMGO and they accepted the VMGO as essential in their education at San Isidro College.

Item No. 13 “The VMGO are adapted to the educational needs of the local, regional, and national community” was responded with a yes by a 97.32% of the respondents. This means that the SED’s VMGO addressed the needs of the community. It is good to note that the teacher graduates of SIC are employed in the schools in Malaybalay and neighboring places in Bukidnon. This implies that the SED graduates of SIC respond to the need of the community, locally and regionally.

Item No. 14 “The institution includes among its goals the completion of an adequate program of general education by each of its students” was answered yes by majority of the respondents. There were however four from the students and one from the faculty who responded with an *uncertain* response. It would be good to note that the Program that the SED follow is mandated by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and that the students are declared as graduates by the President of the College upon completion of the requirements of the degree, hence objective 14 implicitly embed the inclusion of the adequate program of the general education.

In a capsule, majority of the stakeholders’ agreed to the VMGO of the SED. They also indicated that they are aware of these VMGO and that they accepted these VMGO to be the overall *raison d’être* of San Isidro College. Hence, the VMGO of SED are accepted.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The VMGO of the School of Education at San Isidro College could be the compass that leads the students to their destination. As such these VMGO must be clearly articulated by the school’s administrators, faculty, staff, students, alumni and other stakeholders especially in the academe. The academic heartbeats translated to its VMGO gives the direction towards the enthusiasm, passion, and expertise that the teachers bring to the classrooms.

The findings of the study revealed that the stakeholders strongly agreed that the objectives of the SED clearly state the intent found in the SIC graduate attributes of being God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service-oriented. The online consultation with the stakeholders revealed that they were aware of the VMGO of the SED. They accepted these VGMO as the essential *raison d’être* of San Isidro College’ existence in this part of Mindanao. Therefore, the VMGO of the School of Education are accepted. The Philosophy and the formulated objectives of the SED will be incorporated in the report for the PAASCU accreditation.

Based from the findings and conclusions of the study, the SED will espouse the objectives and include these under its mission and vision. Since the VMGO reflects the policies, priorities and shared reflection on the values, beliefs and aspirations of the school community these have to be constantly revisited by the stakeholders, and updated to keep abreast with the social and cultural milieu of the time.

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